

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: Nathoo****FIRST NAME: Rishma****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID),

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 0%

The author used the following software: MSWord – Office 365 on (Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. Which of the following is an incorrect use of an apostrophe?
 - St Giles's splits into Woodstock and Banbury Roads.¹**
 - Jesus's methods were unpopular with the ruling classes
 - The cat has been out in the rain, and it is muddy.
 - Strong tea is sometimes called builders' tea.

2. What guidance does the ACA-401 Coursepack provide on using dashes and hyphens
 - Use dashes between multiple classifying adjectives: absolutes that are or are not, such as unique, English, and black.
 - Hyphens show that some text is missing, usually from a quotation.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 5th ed. (Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024), 16.

- Dashes, particularly the n-dash, can be used similarly to commas and brackets.²**
- Add a hyphen after an introductory adverb, adverbial phrase, or subordinate clause.
3. What does the Turabian Rule of Style outline as the common questions answered in an argument?
- Was an invalid claim made to support a warrant?
- What exceptions validate a claim?
- Does the evidence contradict the argument?
- What principles and points of view make the reasoning relevant?³**
4. What guidance does the Turabian Rule of Style say about correctly planning the first draft of your research?
- Create a patchwork of sources.
- Draft a storyboard and build an outline where information is organized and put into layers.⁴**
- Always mirror the assignment.
- Be sure to narrate a story that is compelling and personal.
5. Which is the correct sequencing of the four dissertation components?

² Ibid., 20.

³ Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers* (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 59–67.

⁴ Ibid., 68–69.

- Dissertation concept paper, dissertation prospectus, dissertation, and dissertation manuscript.**⁵
- Dissertation prospectus, dissertation concept paper, dissertation, and dissertation manuscript.
- Dissertation concept paper, dissertation, dissertation manuscript, and dissertation prospectus.
- Dissertation concept paper, dissertation prospectus, dissertation manuscript, and dissertation.
6. Which of the following sources is unhelpful?
- Sources obtained from news stations.**⁶
- Sources collected for evidence.
- Sources obtained from other researchers.
- Sources for introductory overviews.
7. Which statement about the methodology chapter of a dissertation is correct?
- A hypothesis and data are part of a qualitative research paper.
- Measures are always specific variables, be it qualitative or quantitative research.
- Bias is expected and thus does not need acknowledgment.

⁵ James Jr. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 2nd ed. (Tallahassee, FL: Florida State University, 2017), 13.

⁶ Turabian et al., 35-37.

- Details the scientific assumptions that guide selecting methods to answer the research questions.⁷**

8. Which of the procedures listed below before collecting data is incorrect?

- Use physical or virtual spaces to store collected data.
- Consent forms from participants are not required if the purpose of the data collection has been verbally explained and consented to.⁸**
- Avoid plagiarism by understanding the appropriate inclusion and citation of copyright materials and including permission letters in the dissertation appendices.
- Select and train individuals who will participate in the dissertation research.

9. Which of the following is not on the checklist for completing a dissertation manuscript?

- Seek a major professor review of the manuscript (and other co-authors as appropriate).
- Complete all necessary forms and procedures for dissertation submission to the university.⁹**
- Select a peer-reviewed journal for submission of the manuscript
- Prepare the manuscript according to the manuscript guidelines of the journal selected for submission

⁷ James Sampson Jr., 34-39.

⁸ James Sampson Jr., 50-52.

⁹ Ibid., 82-83.

10. Which of the following is a correct statement about the critical genres' methodology in qualitative research?

- It is grounded in theory that assumes that class and sexual orientation structure society and oppress marginalized groups.¹⁰**
- It believes that theory and practice are connected and, when connected, lead to action and social improvement.
- It is applied when little information about a research interest is known, requiring the piecing of related topics to find meaning.
- It is a philosophy to understand the meaning of a lived experience.

¹⁰ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End. 4th ed.* (Los Angeles, CA: SAGE, 2019), 168–83.

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Turabian, Kate L., Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and The University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations. Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.